

Tuning the appearance of Marcus inversion region for intermolecular electron transfer (ET) reactions in micellar media[†]

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Abstract : In this mini-review we present a concise account of the results of our research on photoinduced electron transfer (ET) processes in micellar media, which we have been actively pursuing in our group for last one decade. Though Marcus inversion behavior is easy to observe for intramolecular ET reactions as well as for charge recombination reactions in contact ion pairs, the difficulty of observing such inversion behavior for intermolecular ET reactions under diffusive condition is a long lasting problem. The two most important factors that act against the observation of Marcus inversion for intermolecular ET reactions are : (i) diffusion of the reactants, which imposes a maximum limit for the observed reaction rate such that the true ET rates, which are faster than the diffusional rate of the reactants, are not possible to be estimated for such systems, and (ii) the non-availability of suitable donor and acceptor series to reach a very high reaction exergonicity ($-\Delta G^\ominus$) such that it is difficult to reach the farthest part of the inverted region where the true ET rates in the donor-acceptor encounter pairs become inherently slower than the diffusional rate of the reactants. In our studies, different micellar systems have been judiciously used as the reaction media to overcome the above limiting factors and accordingly the Marcus inversion behavior for the intermolecular ET reactions could be observed very easily. In these studies, the advantages of the micellar systems have been taken with respect to the following considerations, i.e. (i) the diffusion of the reactants inside the micelles will be highly retarded such that the ET reactions can effectively be considered as occurring under a non-diffusive condition of the reactants and (ii) the solvent relaxation dynamics in micellar media will be substantially slow such that the ET reactions in micelles will effectively occur under a situation of non-equilibrium solvent reorganization where the effective contribution of the solvent reorganization energy towards the activation barrier for the ET reactions will be reduced significantly and accordingly the onset of the Marcus inversion will be shifted towards the lower exergonicity region in comparison to that under very fast solvent relaxation condition. In fact, our studies in different micellar media using various donor-acceptor systems have unequivocally established for the first time the easy observation of Marcus inversion region for intermolecular ET reactions. Besides the observation of Marcus inversion region, we have also investigated other important aspects that might change the kinetics of ET reactions in micellar media, namely the effect of intervening surfactant chain, effect of temperature, distant dependence of the reactants, etc. In this short review we briefly present the results of these studies, with special emphasis to the observation of Marcus inversion and its tuning using micellar systems.

Keywords : Intermolecular electron transfer, micelles, electron transfer dynamics, Marcus inversion.

Introduction

Chemical reactivity and its tuning is an important aspect of research in chemical sciences. Chemical reactivity deals with various factors that govern both the reaction rates and the reaction mechanisms by which the reactions transpire. Knowing the nature of the intermediate steps is also an important aspect to understand the chemical reactions in detail. Among all the chemical processes,

electron transfer (ET) is undoubtedly the most fundamental reaction and is found to be involved as the initial step in numerous chemical systems of vast technological and biological importance, such as information storage, energy conversion, photosynthesis, respiration, etc.¹⁻²¹. ET is in fact ubiquitous in chemistry and biology and this veracity of the ET reactions that prompted Prof. R. A. Marcus to develop the theoretical understanding of the

[†]In honour of Professor Jai P. Mittal.

ET dynamics²¹⁻²⁸, which ultimately brought him the Nobel Prize in chemistry in the year 1992. As evident from Marcus ET theory, to understand the dynamics of ET processes in detail one needs to know the following important aspects, (i) the electronic coupling between the reacting partners, (ii) the energetics for the condition of the electronic resonance for the reactant and the product states, and (iii) the barrier crossing dynamics. These three aspects are essential for both homogeneous and heterogeneous ET reactions and are adequately incorporated in the semi-classical form of the Marcus ET theory.

The study of ET reactions in restricted heterogeneous media, like in micelles, has attracted considerable attention in the last few decades²⁹⁻³³. The main interest in such studies arises due to the fact that in many practical applications of the ET reactions, e.g. in solar energy conversion or in its storage, the ET reactions are needed to be carried out in heterogeneous media²⁹⁻³³. Unlike the homogeneous media, the heterogeneous media often provide an opportunity to separate the primary products of the ET reactions, mainly through the increase in the lifetime of the primary species, and thus preventing the most energy wasting back ET process quite significantly²⁹⁻³³. Among different heterogeneous media, reactions in micellar solutions have attracted the most attention of the researchers in order to understand the effect of the topology of the reaction media on the mechanism and dynamics of the reactions and further to understand if one can control the kinetics of a reaction by simple manipulation of the microscopic environment³⁴⁻⁴⁰. The importance of the ET reactions in micellar systems is also due to the structural resembles of the micelles with different biological membranes⁴¹⁻⁴⁴. Though lot of efforts have been made to understand ET processes in normal homogeneous solvents, literature reports on ET dynamics in heterogeneous media including micelles are very limited. In the present review, we briefly discuss our results on ET studies in micellar media involving different donor-acceptor pairs with emphasis to various intriguing factors that determine the ET dynamics in such systems and thus modulate the Marcus inversion behavior. An overview of the theoretical background of ET dynamics has also been presented for a better perception of the observed results related to the intermolecular ET reactions in micellar media.

Theoretical background of the ET dynamics

A simple but a very important theoretical formalism for the ET dynamics has been developed by Prof. Marcus in 1956²¹⁻²⁸, where the ET rates are described in terms of the small number of experimentally accessible parameters. The classical ET theory as given by Marcus is based on two important concepts, one is the Franck-Condon principle and the other is the law of conservation of energy. According to this theory, ET from the donor (D) to the acceptor (A) takes place only at the transition state (TS; cf. Fig. 1), where the nuclei of the reactant (D/A) and the product (D⁺/A⁻) states do not undergo any displacement during ET and accordingly the energy of the system remains conserved^{20-28,45-52}.

Fig. 1. Schematic presentation of the free energies for the reactant and the product states in an ET reaction. ΔG^0 is the free energy change for the ET reaction, ΔG^\ddagger is the free energy of activation and λ is the total reorganization energy. TS represents the transition state. In the Marcus ET theory the free energies of the reactant and product states are the quadratic functions (harmonic approximation) of the solvent coordinate.

To represent the energetics of the ET reactions, Marcus considered the free energy of the reactant and product states as the quadratic functions of the reaction coordinate. For ET reaction in fast relaxing polar solvents, reaction coordinate can simply be considered as equivalent to the solvent polarization coordinate because the reorganization energy involving intramolecular relaxation is relatively very less. Thus, the free energy surfaces for the reactant and product states and their crossing at the TS can pictorially be shown as in Fig. 1, where the en-

ergy terms, ΔG^0 , ΔG^* and λ represent the free energy change for the ET reaction, the free energy of activation and the total reorganization energy for the ET reaction respectively. In a fast relaxing polar solvent, the term λ can practically be considered as equal to the solvent reorganization energy λ_s , though in true sense λ is equal to $(\lambda_s + \lambda_i)$, where λ_i is the intramolecular reorganization energy. To be mentioned here that in this presentation the reactant and product states are actually the supramolecular systems that consists the reacting species along with their surrounding solvent environments^{2-4,19-28,45-52}.

Thermal fluctuations in the nuclear and solvent coordinates effectively lead the reactant state to reach the TS geometry where ET takes place from the donor to the acceptor moiety. Thus, ET is basically viewed as the case of free energy surface crossing, equivalent to that considered in many other chemical reactions. During the course of the ET reaction, it is considered that both the reactant and the product states maintain an equilibrium distribution along the reaction coordinate (solvent polarization axis) because the reaction medium is a fast relaxing polar solvent^{2-4,19-28,45-52}. In the description of the ET reaction, it is also assumed that the relaxation along the intramolecular (nuclear) coordinates of the reactants is also very fast. Based on the classical ET theory, as proposed by Marcus, upon reaching the TS by thermal fluctuations in the nuclear and solvent coordinates, the reactant state converts to the product state with unit probability. Thus, reactive trajectories cross the barrier top only once on the free energy surface. Once the reactant crosses the TS region, and the product state is formed with excess energy, the system quickly dissipates the excess energy into the surrounding fast relaxing solvent bath⁵³⁻⁵⁵ and thus the product state attends the thermal equilibrium almost immediately following the ET process at the free energy surface crossing.

Considering the semi-classical treatment of the Marcus ET theory, the rate constant k_{et} of the ET reaction, $D/A \rightarrow D^+/A^-$, is related to the free-energy change (ΔG^0) of the reaction by the following quadratic equation.

$$k_{et} = \frac{2\pi}{h} \frac{V_{el}^2}{\sqrt{4\pi\lambda_s k_B T}} \exp\left[-\frac{(\Delta G^0 + \lambda)^2}{4\lambda_s k_B T}\right] \quad (1)$$

where, V_{el} is the measure of the electronic coupling be-

tween the reactant (D/A) and the product (D^+/A^-) states at the free energy surface crossing, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the absolute temperature and $\lambda (= \lambda_s + \lambda_i)$ is the total reorganization energy. Physically, the term λ_i is the measure of the reorganization energy associated with the changes in the intramolecular vibrational modes of the reactants following ET reaction, and can be expressed as^{24,47,48},

$$\lambda_i = \frac{1}{2} \sum_j f_j (\Delta q_{e,j})^2 \quad (2)$$

where f_j is the force constant for the j vibrational mode and $\Delta q_{e,j}$ is the change in the equilibrium nuclear coordinate for that vibrational mode for going from the reactant to the product state. These parameters can be obtained from vibrational spectroscopy and/or X-ray structures and accordingly λ_i can be calculated. For most organic donor-acceptor systems the value of λ_i is found to be in the range of 0.2-0.3 eV^{2,4,18,19,50}. The solvent reorganization energy λ_s is a measure of the rearrangement of the polar solvent molecules around the reacting system following the ET reaction. A reasonable estimate of λ_s can be obtained by considering the reacting species (donors and acceptors) as the effective spheres, and considering the dielectric continuum model for the surrounding solvent. Based on these assumptions, it can be shown that the λ_s can be expressed as^{2-4,19-28,45-52},

$$\lambda_s = e^2 \left(\frac{1}{2r_D} + \frac{1}{2r_A} - \frac{1}{r} \right) \left(\frac{1}{n^2} - \frac{1}{\epsilon} \right) \quad (3)$$

where r_D is the radius of the donor, r_A is the radius of the acceptor, r is the distance between the donor and the acceptor centers in the encounter complex, n is the refractive index of the solvent and ϵ is the static dielectric constant of the solvent.

The most important prediction of Marcus ET theory (*cf.* eq. (1)) is the existence of the inverted region for the ET rates at the higher exergonicity region where λ exceeds $-\Delta G^0$. The energy gap (free energy change, ΔG^0) dependence of the ET rate constants, as predicted by Marcus ET theory can be qualitatively shown as in Fig. 2. As indicated in the upper panel of this figure, the energy gap dependence of the ET rate constants can be classified into three regions : (i) the normal region, where

$-\Delta G^0 < \lambda_s$, (ii) the barrierless region, where $-\Delta G^0 = \lambda_s$ and (iii) the inverted region, where $-\Delta G^0 > \lambda_s$. In the normal region, as predicted by eq. (1), the value of $(\Delta G^0 + \lambda)^2$ decreases on increasing the reaction exergonicity ($-\Delta G^0$) and accordingly the free energy of activation (ΔG^*) decreases causing an increase in the ET rate. As the reaction exergonicity reaches the barrierless condition, the value of $(\Delta G^0 + \lambda)^2$ and hence ΔG^* reduces to zero and thus the ET rate reaches to its maximum value. In the inverted region, as the value of $(\Delta G^0 + \lambda)^2$ starts increasing again on increasing the reaction exergonicity (cf. eq. (1)), the value ΔG^* also increases accordingly and thus the ET rate should show a gradual decrease in this region with the increasing $-\Delta G^0$ value. Therefore, following Marcus ET theory, the ET rate constants should show a bell-shaped curve on plotting against ΔG^0 values as shown in the lower panel of Fig. 2.

The Marcus inversion region for ET reactions has a tremendous implication in the applied areas, as in most ET systems, following the forward charge separation reaction, the back ET reaction also subsequently takes place, which significantly reduces the effective outcome of the forward ET process, if the rate of the back ET reaction is not substantially slower compared to that of the forward ET reaction². In photoinduced ET reaction, it can be easily perceived that the reverse ET reaction, which produces back the ground state reactants, always occurs at a much higher exergonicity than that of the forward ET reaction. In such cases, if the exergonicity for the forward ET reaction is closer to the barrierless region, the back ET will naturally occur in the inverted region such that the rate of the back ET will be much slower than that of the forward ET. On the contrary, if the exergonicity for the forward ET is far into the normal region, the back

Fig. 2. Free energy curves for the reactant (R) and the product (P) states for the three regions of the reaction exergonicity ($-\Delta G^0$), namely the normal region, barrierless condition and the inverted region, as are shown in the upper panel. The theoretically predicted inverted bell-shaped Marcus correlation curve for the ET rates is shown in the lower panel.

ET can occur closer to the barrierless region, causing the rate of the back ET faster than that of the forward ET. In designing an efficient photoinduced charge separation system, it is always desired that the forward ET is carried out at a rate much higher than that of the back ET process. As the previous discussion suggests, this can be easily achieved by choosing the systems for which the exergonicity for the forward ET reaction is quite close to the barrierless situation such that the back ET is invariably slow than the forward reaction. Thus, by taking the advantage of this relationship, it might be possible to control or modulate the ET reactions; a classic example being the primary charge separation step in photosynthesis that occurs in nature with its maximum efficiency².

Motivation for the intermolecular ET studies in micellar media

Although the prediction of the bell-shaped curve for the ET rates versus the free energy of the reactions (*cf.* Fig. 2) was made by Prof. Marcus long back in mid fifties, it took more than 25 years to obtain the first experimental verification of this inversion behavior for the ET reactions. It was Closs and Miller, who first demonstrated the Marcus inversion behavior for the ET rates experimentally in 1984, using covalently linked D-A molecules as the ET systems⁵⁶⁻⁵⁹. Thereafter, for many of such intramolecular ET systems the Marcus inversion behavior has been convincingly demonstrated⁶⁰⁻⁶⁸. The Marcus inversion behavior has also been convincingly demonstrated for a large number of cases involving charge recombination reactions⁶⁹⁻⁷². However, for intermolecular ET reactions, where the donor (D) and the acceptor (A) units are isolated molecules in a diffusing medium, the Marcus inversion behavior is very difficult to be demonstrated. Thus contrary to the previous systems, reports on Marcus inversion in bimolecular ET reactions are not only very rare but are also not that convincing in most cases^{73,74}, except the reports of Guldi and co-workers^{75,76} for some ET systems involving fullerenes as the reactants and slow electron transfer across zeolite-solution interface reported by Fukuzumi *et al.*^{77,78}. This is primarily because the diffusion of reactants (D and A) is required in the first step to bring the reactants together to form the encounter complex where the actual ET reaction takes place². In such cases, the diffusional rate of the reactants effectively becomes the rate determining step even though the true ET in the encounter complex can occur with a much higher rate than the diffusional rate of the reac-

ants. Thus, in intermolecular ET reactions, the diffusion of the reactants imposes an upper limit (k_d) for the observed reaction rate constant (k_q) and consequently masks the observation of the expected Marcus inversion behavior. Thus, in such cases, the observed reaction rate constant k_q , which is often estimated by using fluorescence quenching method, is seen to initially increase on increasing the reaction exergonicity ($-\Delta G^0$) as long as the reactions are far into the normal region. As the reaction exergonicity becomes reasonably high, the true ET rate in the encounter complex becomes faster than the diffusional rate k_d , causing the overall reaction to become diffusion controlled. Thus for a large exergonicity region for which the true ET rate is faster than the diffusional rate, the observed reaction rate constant k_q maintains its limiting value equal to that of the diffusional rate constant k_d . The situation is schematically shown in Fig. 3 and this typical behavior of saturation of the k_q values to the diffusional controlled limit of k_d is commonly known as the Rehm-Weller behavior⁷⁹. Obviously, the inversion behavior in the k_q values can be possible to observe if the reaction exergonicity can be made exceedingly high (far into the inverted region) such that the true ET rate again becomes slower than the diffusional rate⁸⁰. However, finding a homologous donor-acceptor series to reach such an extremely high reaction exergonicity is often difficult and accordingly in most of the intermolecular ET reactions under diffusive condition the observed k_q values are seen to display the typical Rehm-Weller behavior.

Fig. 3. Presentation of the typical Rehm-Weller behavior for the observed reaction rate constant (k_q) vs reaction exergonicity ($-\Delta G^0$) for intermolecular ET reactions under diffusive condition. The nature of the theoretically predicted inverted bell-shaped Marcus correlation curve for the ET rates is also shown for comparison.

Following the above discussions, it is evident that it is really a challenge to the researchers working in the field of intermolecular ET reactions to design a methodology to overcome the above limiting factors such that the Marcus inversion behavior can be easily observed and tuned to find better applicability of such ET reactions. In our studies, to surmount the above limiting factors, we have judiciously used different organized assemblies such as micelles and reverse micelles as the reaction media for the investigation of the kinetics of intermolecular ET reactions. The merits for the selection of such self-organized assemblies as the reaction media are based on the following considerations. (i) The reactants in the micellar microenvironment will always remain entangled within the surfactant chains and thus the mobility of the reactants in these systems will be largely retarded³⁴⁻³⁹. In fact, the diffusion of the reactants in these systems can be prevented so largely that the intermolecular ET reactions in these media can effectively occur under nondiffusive condition and thus the effect of the reactant diffusion in masking the Marcus inversion behavior in homogeneous solution can be avoided. (ii) The effective contribution of the solvent reorganization energy λ_s on the ET reaction is expected to be quite less in micellar media compared to that in bulk homogeneous solution with similar polarity. This is expected because the solvent motion in micellar system should be much retarded than in homogeneous solvent media⁸¹ and accordingly the solvent relaxation in the former case cannot equilibrate the reactant state during the progress of the ET reaction. Due to the less contribution of λ_s on the ET reaction in micellar media, the Marcus inversion region ($-\Delta G^0 > \lambda$) is expected to move towards a relatively lower exergonicity in comparison to that in homogeneous polar solvent media. Hence, instead of increasing the exergonicity for the intermolecular ET reaction to an unreasonably high value, as required in the case of the homogeneous solutions, the Marcus inversion for such ET systems in the micellar media can be easily observed at a relatively lower exergonicity values.

Marcus inversion behavior for intermolecular ET reactions in micellar media

To substantiate the above proposition that micellar systems can be the conducive media for the observation of Marcus inversion behavior for intermolecular ET re-

actions, we have investigated the kinetics of the ET reactions between excited coumarin dyes (acts as the electron acceptors) and ground state aromatic amines (act as the electron donors) in different micelles using fluorescence quenching measurements⁸²⁻⁹¹. The micellar systems used in these studies include sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS), Triton X-100 (TX-100), cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), P123 triblock copolymer, etc. The bimolecular quenching constants (k_q) obtained for different coumarin-amine systems using mainly the time-resolved fluorescence measurements are correlated with the free-energy changes (ΔG^0) in these ET systems. Since the fluorescence lifetime of the coumarin dyes are only few nanoseconds, it is evident that the fluorescence of the coumarin dyes in the micelles is quenched only by the micelle solubilized amine donors. Moreover, within the timescale of the fluorescence quenching in the present systems (also occur in the nanosecond time scales), there should not be any exchange of the quenchers between the micelle and the aqueous phase outside. Based on these assumptions and also considering that there is no significant diffusion of the reactants in the micellar phase, the non-single-exponential fluorescence decays of the coumarin dyes observed in the micelles in the presence of the amine quenchers were attributed to the distant dependent distribution of the quenchers around the excited acceptors⁸². Interestingly, in the absence of the amine quenchers, the fluorescence decays of the coumarin dyes in the micelles were single-exponential in nature. To obtain the average picture of the quenching process, the fluorescence decays of the coumarin dyes in the presence of the amine quenchers were analyzed following a bi-exponential function and the average fluorescence lifetime τ_{av} of the dyes in these cases were estimated by using the weighted contributions of the two decay times to the integrated fluorescence intensity under the decay curves. The fluorescence lifetime, τ_0 , of the dyes in the micelles in the absence of the quenchers were estimated by analyzing the corresponding fluorescence decays using a single-exponential function. Thus, knowing the changes in the τ_0/τ_{av} ratio as a function of the quencher concentration used, the quenching constant (k_q) values were estimated following the standard Stern-Volmer relation⁹². Appropriate correction for the quencher concentration in the micellar Stern layer, the solubilization site of the reactants, was

also applied to estimate the true k_q values for the present ET systems in different micellar media. Fig. 4 shows the typical k_q vs ΔG^0 plot obtained for the coumarin-aromatic amine systems in P123 triblock copolymer micellar media⁹⁰. To be mentioned that similar k_q vs ΔG^0 plots were also obtained for the coumarin-amine ET system in all other micellar media investigated in the present study⁸²⁻⁹¹. As evident from the plot in Fig. 4, a bell-shaped Marcus correlation curve is clearly demonstrated for the intermolecular ET reactions carried out in micellar media. It is interesting to note here that for the similar coumarin-amine ET systems, the k_q vs ΔG^0 plot showed the typical Rehm-Weller behavior, when the ET reac-

tions were carried out in a polar homogeneous solvent, e.g. in acetonitrile solution⁹³⁻⁹⁵. Thus, it is evident from our results that the micellar systems provide a conducting media to observe the Marcus inversion behavior for intermolecular ET reactions. In fact, a clear Marcus inversion behavior for intermolecular ET reactions in micellar media was convincingly demonstrated by us for the first time, though such inversion behaviors for intramolecular ET reactions were known in the literature for quite long. After the initial report from our group on the observation of Marcus inversion behavior for intermolecular ET reactions in micellar media, many ET studies on bimolecular ET reactions in confined and organized assemblies have been reported in the literature, with an aim to understand various aspects of ET dynamics in such media, especially to understand the reasons behind the easy observation of Marcus inversion behavior for the intermolecular ET reactions in such micro-heterogeneous media^{82-91,96-102}.

Apart from the demonstration of the inverted bell-shaped correlation between the observed ET rate constants and the driving force, we have also investigated the intricate details of the micellar ET kinetics by critical analysis of the observed results and by careful examination of the available literature reports. It has been established that the standard diffusional kinetic model¹⁰³⁻¹⁰⁷, which is normally used by many researchers to analyze the slow reaction kinetics (microseconds) in micellar media, is not suitable to describe the observed ET kinetics for the present coumarin-amine systems, where quenching occurs in the nanosecond timescale (within the fluorescence lifetime of the coumarin dyes)⁸²⁻⁸⁴. According to the standard diffusional kinetic model used to analyze the results of slow quenching reactions in the micellar phase, the quenchers are assumed to migrate between the micelle and the aqueous phases within the quenching time scale. In such cases, the excited fluorophores in the micelles are modeled to undergo quenching with a unified quenching rate constant (k_q) per quencher occupancy in the micelle. In the present systems, since the solubility of both the fluorophores (coumarin dyes) and quenchers (aromatic amines) are very low in aqueous solution, it is quite expected that both the reactants are preferentially solubilized in the micellar phase. It is further established that the solubilization sites for both the reactants in the present cases are the intermediately polar Stern layer of the mi-

Fig. 4. Upper panel shows the Marcus bell-shaped correlation observed for the rate constants of intermolecular ET reactions between coumarins and aromatic amines in P123 triblock copolymer micellar media against the free energy changes of the ET reactions. The typical Rehm-Weller behavior observed for the similar coumarin-aromatic amine systems in homogeneous acetonitrile solution is shown in the lower panel.

cellular phase⁸². Since in the present cases the reactants are mainly solubilized in the micellar phase, the exit rate constant of the quencher (or the acceptor) from the micelle to the aqueous phase is expected to be quite slow. In fact, in micellar solution, the exit of the reactants from the micelle to the aqueous phase is reported to occur mostly in the microsecond time scale^{103–107}, whereas the fluorescence lifetime of the coumarin dyes investigated in the present work are all in the nanosecond time scale. Thus, the excited coumarin dyes in the present systems should be quenched by the amines within their nanosecond fluorescence lifetimes such that a reasonable quenching effect can be observed experimentally. Thus, within the nanosecond timescale of the quenching interaction in the present systems, there will be hardly any entry or exit of the quenchers from the micelles. Additionally, under the condition of restricted diffusion of the reactants in the micelle, assumption of the overall rate constant as, $\bar{n}k'_q$ (i.e. k'_q multiplied by the average quencher occupancy number, \bar{n} must be an over simplification. Thus, for the present systems the observed fluorescence decays of the coumarin dyes in the micelles in the presence of the quencher amines could not be fitted following the above standard diffusional quenching kinetic model^{103–107}. Rather, for the present systems, it was better realized that the ET reactions in the micelles effectively take place under nondiffusive condition, because the diffusional rates (k_d) of the reactants in the micelles, as calculated from the estimated microviscosity values in micellar media, are found to be slower than the observed quenching rates (k_q)^{82–91}. Thus, it is proposed that in the present systems the observed quenching kinetics is determined mainly by the radial distribution of the quenchers around the excited fluorophore in the micelle. Recently Tavernier *et al.* have also indicated that the radial distribution function of the quenchers plays a significant role in determining the observed ET kinetics in micellar media¹⁰⁸.

The most important finding in our studies on intermolecular ET reactions in micellar media is the onset of Marcus inversion at an exergonicity ($-G^0$) value of about 0.7 eV, which is much lower in energy than that expected if the solvent reorganization energy λ_s (≥ 1.0 eV) was fully contributed towards the ET reaction². Present observation is not unexpected if we consider that the solvent relaxation dynamics in organized assemblies is much slower than that in polar homogeneous media. For the

present systems, to have an estimate for the solvent reorganization energy λ_s , we have adopted the approach given by Fayer and co-workers for the calculation of the parameter in the micellar Stern/Palisade layer in micellar solution^{38,108,109}. According to their approach, the micelles are viewed as consisting of three regions, with low polarity micellar core having dielectric properties similar to that of the hydrocarbon solvents, the medium polarity spherical shell around the core (Stern/Palisade layer) with an intermediate dielectric constant, and the bulk aqueous phase around the micelle having dielectric properties similar to that of water. Thus, the λ_s values in the Stern layer of different micelles were calculated following Fayer and co-workers, considering the reported core diameter and the Stern/Palisade layer thickness of the concerned micelles. The λ_s values thus estimated in different micelles for the donor-acceptor close contact situation are found to be in the range of about 1.0 eV^{82–91}. To be mentioned that the λ_s values thus estimated for different micelles are supposed to be their lower limit, because in the micellar systems the shortest average separation for the reacting donor-acceptor pairs is supposed to be more than their contact distance. In other words, in micellar solution, it is quite likely that for most of the interacting donor-acceptor pairs the reactants are not in physical contact but are on average separated by an intervening surfactant chain^{85,89}. Accordingly, we expect that in such system the actual λ_s values could be somewhat higher than the above estimates made on basis of the close-contact donor-acceptor pairs. However, these estimates are still very useful as they give us an idea about the possible lower limit of the λ_s values in such systems.

Considering that the λ_s value in P123 block copolymer micelle is ~ 1.0 eV, it is apparent from Fig. 4 (upper panel) that for the present coumarin-amine systems in this micellar solution the onset of inversion in the ET rates occurs at much lower exergonicity than expected. These results are thus indicative of the fact that the solvent reorganization process in micellar system is substantially slow such that it is not able to keep the reacting ET systems to their equilibrium distribution during the course of the ET reaction. In other words, in micellar systems the ET reactions between the donor-acceptor pairs effectively occur under the nonequilibrium distribution of the reactant state along the solvent reorganization coordinate,

a concept that explicitly taken into consideration in the formalism of the two dimensional ET (2DET) model as proposed and analyzed critically by Sumi and Marcus²⁸. For the micellar ET reactions, we thus strongly feel that it is not the conventional ET theory, but the 2DET theory is most useful in explaining and correlating the observed results related to the Marcus inversion behavior. According to the 2DET theory, the ET reaction is viewed to proceed through the intramolecular coordinate (involving low frequency vibrational modes of the reactants) even when the reactants are in a non-equilibrium configuration with respect to the solvent reorganization coordinate. It is assumed that the reorganization along the intramolecular coordinate occurs much faster than the ET process and accordingly the reactant and product states always maintain their equilibrium distribution along this coordinate. The progress of the ET reactions in accordance to the 2DET theory is visualized as shown in Fig. 5 where ET takes place with a suitable rate at any nonequilibrium solvent coordinate for the reactant states. The high-frequency vibrational modes of the product states can also be involved in the ET process as shown in the upper panel of Fig. 5, though in most cases the involvement of the high-frequency vibrational modes can be neglected for a qualitative or semi-quantitative correlation of the observed results following 2DET model.

Based on the 2DET model, the free energies of the reactant and product states can be expressed as the quadratic functions of X and q coordinates as given by the following relation^{28,50}.

$$G_r(X, q) = \lambda_s X^2 + \lambda_i q^2 \quad (4)$$

$$G_p(X, q) = \lambda_s (X - 1)^2 + \lambda_i (q - 1)^2 + \Delta G^0 \quad (5)$$

where the terms λ_s , λ_i and ΔG^0 have the same meaning as discussed earlier. In these expressions, the role of the high-frequency vibrational modes is not considered as they are not essential for a qualitative or semi-quantitative correlation of the experimental results. In the two-dimensional model for the ET reaction, the basic assumption is that the relaxation along the intramolecular q coordinate is much faster than that along solvation coordinate X . Thus, the distribution of the reactant and product states along the q coordinate always maintains the thermal equilibrium condition. However, the distribution of the reactant state along the X coordinate often may remain in a

Fig. 5. Conceptual potential energy diagram for 2DET reaction is shown in the upper panel. ET is shown to occur along intramolecular vibrational coordinate with nonequilibrium configuration along solvent coordinate. Participation of the high-frequency vibrational modes of the product states is also indicated. The isoenergy contours for the reactant and product potential energy surfaces are shown in lower panel in accordance with the 2DET model. ET occurs along the intramolecular q coordinate while the solvent reorganization occurs along the X coordinate. The normalized (X, q) coordinates for the equilibrium reactant and product states are customarily placed at $(0, 0)$ and $(1, 1)$ positions, respectively. The line C-C represents the transition state curve corresponding to the crossing of the reactant and product state potential energy surfaces.

nonequilibrium condition due to slow solvent relaxation dynamics, and thus may evolve with time due to solvation process during the progress of the ET reaction. Therefore, in 2DET model one can visualize the ET reaction to occur along q , for different nonequilibrium X coordinate of the reactant state. Thus, at any X , considering the ET reaction to be non-adiabatic in nature, the ET rate constant $k(X)$ can be expressed as^{28,50,110,118},

$$k(X) = \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} \frac{V_{el}^2}{\sqrt{4\pi\lambda k_B T}} \exp \left\{ -\frac{\Delta G^*(X)}{k_B T} \right\} \quad (6)$$

Important to note here that in the above equation the free energy of activation $\Delta G^*(X)$ is a function of X coordinate. Using expressions (4) and (5) for the free energies of the reactant and product states, and assuming no participation of high frequency vibrational modes, expression for $\Delta G^*(X)$ can be obtained as,

$$\Delta G^*(X) = \frac{[\lambda_s(1-2X) + \Delta G^0 + \lambda_i]^2}{4\lambda_i} \quad (7)$$

For the photoinduced ET reactions in the present coumarin-amine systems, since the reactant state corresponds to the excited state (S_1) of the coumarin dyes, and since the dipole moments of the excited coumarin dyes are much higher than those in the ground state, immediately after photoexcitation the reactant state will be placed in a nonequilibrium solvent configuration X_g , which is being determined by the position of the ground state potential energy minimum along the X coordinate. The value of X_g can roughly be estimated from the observed differences between the Stokes shifts ($\Delta\nu$) of the coumarin dyes in the micellar solution and in a non-polar solvent where the solvent dielectric interaction is expected to be negligible. Thus, the difference between the above two Stokes' shift ($\Delta(\Delta\nu)$) can be related to X_g following the equation^{50,110-115},

$$2\lambda_s X_g^2 = \Delta(\Delta\nu) \quad (8)$$

The average value of $\Delta(\Delta\nu)$ for the coumarin dyes investigated in different micelles is found to be $\sim 1200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Thus, using a λ_s value of $\sim 1.0 \text{ eV}$, the average X_g value for the present systems is estimated to be about 0.28. Based on eq. (7), and considering the solvent motion to be completely frozen, the contribution of λ_s towards the free energy of activation for the initially prepared reactant state following photoexcitation is expected to be equal to $(1 - 2X_g)\lambda_s$, which is estimated to be $\sim 0.4 \text{ eV}$. This appears to be quite lower than the effective exergonicity of $\sim 0.7 \text{ eV}$ at which the ET rates show the onset of the inversion behavior in P123 micellar media (*cf.* Fig. 4, upper panel). The apparent difference between the estimated $(1 - 2X_g)\lambda_s$ value and the exergonicity for the onset of the Marcus inversion is supposed to be arising mainly due to the contribution of the intramolecular reorganization energy, λ_i (*cf.* eq. (7)). A partial solvent relaxation during the progress of the ET reaction may also contribute to some extent to account for the above differ-

ence between the estimated $(1 - 2X_g)\lambda_s$ value and the exergonicity for the onset of the Marcus inversion.

Other intricate aspects of intermolecular ET kinetics in micellar media

The easy observation of Marcus inversion behavior for intermolecular ET reactions in micellar media naturally instigated a number of important questions. Some of the queries are,

(i) Whether the observation of Marcus inversion is limited to some donor-acceptor systems due to some specific reason or it is a general phenomenon applicable to all kind of donors and acceptors involved in the micellar ET reaction?

(ii) How micellar characteristics (i.e. micellar charge and size) influence the observed ET kinetics?

(iii) Is it possible to tune the exergonicity region for the onset of Marcus inversion behavior?

(iv) Does the observed inversion behavior correlate with the estimated activation barrier for the ET reactions in these systems?

(v) Is there any possibility that an alteration in the diffusion parameters of the reactants at different exergonicity region can be the cause for the observation of the inversion behavior for the ET rates in micellar media.

(vi) Why the ET rates are orders of magnitude slower in micelles compared to that in homogeneous solution when the reactions are carried out under nondiffusive condition, i.e. with the coumarin dyes directly in electron donating amine solvents.

To examine the first point, intermolecular ET reactions were also investigated using other series of the donor-acceptor systems, namely the quinone-aromatic amine systems in SDS micelle^{83,91}. It is seen that ET rates for quinone-amine systems also show an inversion behavior above an exergonicity of about 0.7 eV, quite similar to that observed earlier for the coumarin-aromatic amine systems. Marcus inversion behavior is also seen for coumarin-aliphatic amine systems in other micelle, namely in TX-100⁸⁶. These results thus support our inference that the Marcus inversion behavior is a general phenomenon for intermolecular ET reactions in micellar media.

To address the second point, intermolecular ET studies were carried out in different types of micelles, namely

SDS^{82,83,89}, Triton X-100 (TX-100)^{85,86,88,89}, Pluronic triblock copolymer (P123)⁹⁰, Brij-35 (BJ-35)⁹¹, cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB)⁸⁷ and dodecyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (DTAB)^{87,89}. Interestingly, Marcus inversion behavior was clearly evident in all the micelles studied, irrespective of their cationic, anionic or neutral nature and the differences in their sizes or Stern/Palisade layer thicknesses. Although, depending on the relative propensity of the solvation and the ET rates, appearance of Marcus inversion was found to be shifted towards higher exergonicity in the cationic CTAB and DTAB micelles (~ 1.2 eV) compared to the anionic SDS and neutral P123 and TX-100 micelles. Typical of these shifting for the Marcus inversion along the exergonicity axis is shown in Fig. 6 for three different micelles, TX-100, DTAB and SDS. Nearly 0.6 eV shift for the onset of the Marcus inversion depending on the micellar identity is an interesting observation and suggests the possibility of tuning the ET rates by changing the nature of the micelles. This observation in turn answers our third query on the aspect of tuning the Marcus inversion region for micellar ET reaction.

Fig. 6. Marcus correlation curves for coumarin-amine systems in different micelles. ET rates are calculated from the fast decay components as estimated from the fluorescence up-conversion studies.

We also studied the coumarin-aromatic amine ET systems in TX-100 and P123 micellar solutions as a function of temperature to answer the fourth query^{88,90}. The results of the temperature dependent fluorescence quenching studies in above micellar media indicated the inverse bell-shaped correlation for the estimated activation energy (E_a) for the ET reactions with ΔG^0 as shown in the

upper panel of Fig. 7. Such a correlation is in fact expected from the Marcus ET theory and thus supports our inference that the inversion behavior observed for the intermolecular ET reactions in micellar media is due to the energetic reason only. To explore these systems further and to have an answer for the query number (ν), we have also estimated the translational diffusion coefficient (D_L) of the acceptor dyes on the micellar surface using the time-resolved fluorescence anisotropy measurements^{90,119}. The D_L values for different coumarin dyes used in the present study were calculated from the correlation of the observed time-resolved fluorescence anisotropy results with the theoretically presented two-step model for the fluorescence anisotropy decays in micellar media¹¹⁹⁻¹²¹. The plot of these D_L values for different coumarin dyes as a function of the respective ΔG^0 values for the ET systems involving these coumarin dyes is shown in the lower panel of Fig. 7. It is evident from this figure that the D_L values actually follow a linear relation with ΔG^0 and with only a small change in D_L with the changing ΔG^0 value. Comprehension of these results indicates

Fig. 7. Plot of E_a vs ΔG^0 (upper panel) and D_L vs ΔG^0 (lower panel) for the coumarin-amine systems in P123 micelles.

that the inversion in the ET rates in micellar media at the higher exergonicity region is not due to the alteration in the diffusion parameters of the reactants at different exergonicity regions but due mainly to the changes in the activation barrier for the ET reactions as envisaged from Marcus ET theory.

Ultrafast quenching experiments with the similar donor-acceptor systems in micellar media have also been carried out by us using the femtosecond fluorescence up-conversion instrument⁸⁹. These ultrafast measurements helped us to understand the answers of the other queries put forward in the beginning of this section. The fastest ET rates were estimated simply as the inverse of the shortest lifetime components ($\sim 4\text{--}10$ ps) of the fluorescence decays ($k_{\text{et}} \equiv \tau_{\text{fast}}^{-1}$) and the relatively slower ET rates (k'_{et}) were obtained from the conventional Stern-Volmer analysis of the relatively longer time constants ($\sim 40\text{--}100$ ps) of the fluorescence decays. Both the ET rates (k_{et} and k'_{et} in these cases) exhibited similar Marcus inversion behavior (cf. Fig. 8). Fitting of the Marcus correlation curves corresponding to the correlations of the k_{et} and k'_{et} with ΔG^0 indicated two largely different values for V_{el} , which is known to follow an exponential relation with the separation (r) between the reacting D and A centers (i.e. $V_{\text{el}}(r) = V_{\text{el}}(r_0) \exp [-\beta(r - r_0)]$)^{2,92,122}, where β is the attenuation coefficient, usually assumed as

unity per Å and r_0 is the sum of the D and A radii). From the critical analysis of the observed results it has been suggested that for the isolated donors and acceptors in the micellar media the ultrafast ET component (k_{et}) arises mainly due to those surfactant separated donor-acceptor pairs that are orientated very suitably to give the maximum electronic coupling between the interacting donor and acceptor. Similarly, the slower ET component (k'_{et}) arises mainly due to those surfactant separated donor-acceptor pairs for which the orientation of the interacting donor and acceptor is not very suitable to give very high electronic coupling parameter V_{el} . As the interacting donor-acceptor molecules are on an average separated by an intervening surfactant chain in a micelle, the ET rates are inherently slower in comparison to the ET reactions where the donor and acceptor are in physical contact, e.g. in homogeneous solution when the ET reactions are carried out under non-diffusive condition, i.e. with the coumarin dyes directly in the electron donating amine solvents¹¹⁰⁻¹¹⁵.

Conclusions

In summary, in the present mini review we discuss the main highlight of the results of our ET research in different micellar media. It is found that the expected Marcus inversion behavior for intermolecular ET reactions are easily observed in micellar media though such an inversion normally cannot be observed for intermolecular ET reactions in fast relaxing homogeneous polar solvents. Different intricate aspects of the micellar ET reactions have also been investigated, namely the correlation of the activation barrier with the free energy changes, possibility of differential diffusion of the reactants to cause the Marcus inversion like behavior, if the Marcus correlation curve for the micellar ET reactions can be tuned by some means, etc. It is evident from the discussion made in the present article that the observed ET results in micellar media are the demonstration of the simple but innovative approach to control the kinetics and mechanism of intermolecular ET reactions and to observe and tune the Marcus inversion behavior by using different micelles as the reaction media. Present results show the light to many of the intriguing queries related to micellar ET reactions, a general interest to chemists who strive to control the dynamics and mechanism of a chemical reaction for the maximum outcome of the desired effect.

Fig. 8. Marcus correlation curves for coumarin-amine systems in TX-100 micelles. The fast and the slow ET rates, i.e. k_{et} and k'_{et} respectively (cf. text), were calculated from the fast and the relatively slow lifetime components of the fluorescence decays obtained by fluorescence up-conversion measurements. Both k_{et} and k'_{et} show clear Marcus inversion behavior.

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